

What Does GeoAI Learn About Space? Evidence from DE-9IM Spatial Relations

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Abstract

Geospatial data present unique challenges for artificial intelligence due to their inherent structure, including geometry, scale, and spatial relations. Common transformations into sequences or images often distort essential spatial properties, raising questions about how AI models learn from such representations. This study investigates whether neural networks can learn topological relations defined by the Dimensionally Extended 9-Intersection Model (DE-9IM) directly from raw geometric input. Using a large-scale synthetic dataset of point, line, and polygon pairs, we train multiple architectures on both vector and raster representations to predict DE-9IM relations. Beyond classification performance, we analyze the structure of learned embedding spaces to assess whether spatial concepts such as dimensionality and relation type emerge. Initial findings suggest that models capture non-random spatial structure, particularly geometric dimensionality. The results provide insight into how AI systems internalize spatial knowledge and highlight key challenges in representing geospatial data for learning.

Keywords: GeoAI, Topological Relations, DE-9IM, Spatial Data Models

1. Introduction

Geospatial data pose a long-standing challenge for artificial intelligence (AI) systems (PS Chauhan and Shekhar 2021). Unlike many conventional data modalities, geospatial data are inherently structured by geometry, scale, dimensionality, and spatial relations. To make such data usable for machine learning, they are often transformed into sequences, graphs, or images (Koldasbayeva et al. 2024). While effective in many applications, these transformations frequently discard or distort essential spatial information, i.e., reduce resolution. This raises a fundamental question at the core of GeoAI: how do such representational transformations influence the learning process of AI models? A particularly critical aspect of geospatial data affected by representational transformations is topology. Topological relations describe how spatial objects relate independently of

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metric properties and are therefore central to spatial reasoning. In GIScience, these relations have been formalized deterministically (Clementini, Di Felice, and Oosterom 1993). One of the most established frameworks is the Dimensionally Extended 9-Intersection Model (DE-9IM), which characterizes the spatial relationship between two geometries based on the intersections of their interiors, boundaries, and exteriors. Given two vector geometries, DE-9IM produces a 9-character encoding that captures (i) the dimensionality of the objects involved, (ii) the type of spatial relation (e.g., disjoint, meet, intersect), and (iii) the dimensionality of their intersections. From a GIScience perspective, DE-9IM offers an interpretable description of pairwise spatial relations. From an AI perspective, however, it remains unclear whether such structured spatial knowledge can be learned rather than explicitly computed.

This leads to the central research question of this work: Can AI models learn DE-9IM spatial relations from raw geometric input, and if so, how are these learned relations represented in the embedding space? More specifically, if an AI model is trained to predict DE-9IM encodings for pairs of simple geometries, what organizing principles emerge in its internal representations? Do embeddings cluster by geometric dimensionality (point, line, polygon), by relation type (e.g., disjoint vs. intersect), or by a combination of both? Understanding this is not merely a technical curiosity; it shows directly how AI systems acquire spatial concepts and whether these concepts align with established GIScience theory.

AI has been remarkably successful at learning complex patterns and relationships from data, often acquiring implicit knowledge not explicitly encoded in the training objective. A growing body of research investigates how models learn foundational concepts through exposure to simple tasks. For example, prior work has shown that models trained on basic actions and interactions can develop an internal sense of quantity and even learn to count without direct supervision (Kondapaneni and Perona 2024). Such findings suggest that AI systems may acquire abstract concepts as a byproduct of learning. Spatial relations are similarly fundamental. They support navigation, map understanding, spatial reasoning, and geographic analysis. Yet, unlike numbers or categories, spatial relations are deeply tied to geometry and representation. By studying whether and how AI models learn DE-9IM relations, we aim to bridge a gap between symbolic spatial theory and data-driven learning. This also provides insight into whether GIScience concepts, traditionally defined in rule-based systems, can emerge naturally in neural representations.

2. Methodology

2.1 Data

To investigate spatial relation learning in a controlled setting, we constructed a large-scale synthetic dataset using a custom Python-based geometry generator. The dataset includes zero-dimensional (points), one-dimensional (straight and curved lines), and two-dimensional objects (squares, circles, triangles). All geometries were defined in a discrete $28 * 28$ Cartesian space. For each shape type, instances were systematically generated by varying size (8, 10, 12 units), rotation (45, 90, 135), and position. Shapes were first created at a reference position and then moved across the grid in unit steps along both axes, ensuring full spatial coverage. All geometries were stored in WKT format with unique identifiers. As an example, here is how a square of size 8 is represented in

vector format:

```
sq00000000_POLYGON ((0 0, 0 8, 8 8, 8 0, 0 0))
```

Pairwise combinations of all generated geometries were then created, resulting in approximately 270 million geometry pairs (See Table 1). This is an example of the pairwise combination:

```
sq00000000_POLYGON ((0 0, 0 8, 8 8, 8 0, 0
↪ 0))_st00000000_LINESTRING (0 0, 8 0)
```

For each pair, spatial relations were computed using a PostGIS pipeline, assigning both the full DE-9IM 9-character code (child class) and the corresponding coarse relation type (parent class; e.g., disjoint, touch, intersect). So the final output of this step which made the input vector data is:

```
sq00000000_POLYGON ((0 0, 0 8, 8 8, 8 0, 0
↪ 0))_st00000000_LINESTRING (0 0, 8 0)_FF2101FF2_TOUCH
```

Table 1: Number of generated geometry instances per shape and resulting pairwise combinations.

	square	triangle	straight line	circle	curved line	point
# generated geom	1720	4364	5932	1091	6920	784
square	2958400	7506080	10203040	1876520	11902400	1348480
triangle		19044496	25887248	4761124	30198880	3421376
circle			35188624	6471812	41049440	4650688
straight line				1190281	7549720	855344
curved line					47886400	5425280
point						614656
total number of images					269,990,289	
Total number of child classes					77	
Total number of parent classes					7	

This yielded 77 child classes grouped into 7 parent classes. Two parallel representations were constructed: Vector-based input, consisting of WKT-encoded geometry pairs; Raster-based input, where each geometry was rasterized into a single-band image and combined into a two-channel image using rasterio (see Figure 1 for a visual example). Models were trained on both representations to predict either parent or child classes, enabling a direct comparison of how representation influences the learning of spatial relations.

2.2. Selected Architectures

We trained a set of neural architectures to predict spatial relations from both vector and raster representations of geometry pairs. For raster-based inputs, we used Vision Transformer (ViT) and Convolutional Neural Networks (VGG-style architectures), and for vector-based inputs, we used the Transformer model and Long Short-Term Memory network (LSTM).

All models were trained on two classification tasks:

1. parent-level classification, predicting 7 coarse spatial relation classes (i.e., disjoint, touch,

Figure 1: Example raster representations of geometry pairs used as model input. Each sample is a 28×28 two-channel image, where the two spatial objects are encoded in separate bands and visualized in different colors.

intersect, overlap, contain, equal, and cross)

2. child-level classification, predicting 77 fine-grained DE-9IM classes

Each parent class comprises multiple child classes that represent the same topological relation across different combinations of geometric dimensionality (e.g., point–line, line–polygon, polygon–polygon). For example, the disjoint class includes several DE-9IM encodings corresponding to disjoint configurations between different geometry types. This setup enables a consistent comparison across architectures, input representations, and levels of relational granularity.

3. Initial Results & Conclusion

Initial experiments show that AI models can learn DE-9IM spatial relations from both vector and raster representations, although performance varies across representation types and classification granularity. Raster-based models achieved test accuracies ranging from 41% to 72%, while vector-based models achieved between 61% and 80%, with lower performance generally observed for the more detailed 77-class prediction task compared to the 7 parent classes.

Preliminary results further show consistent, non-random structure in the embedding spaces across multiple architectures. UMAP projections revealed that relations involving geometries of similar dimensionality tend to cluster together, despite the models never being explicitly trained to recognize geometric dimensionality. In particular, point–point, line–line, and polygon–polygon relations formed distinct higher-level groups in the latent space. Within these clusters, spatial relation types also exhibited internal structure, with relations such as *equal* and *disjoint* appearing furthest apart. These findings suggest that the models capture underlying spatial properties rather than solely memorizing labels.

Training on both vector and raster data also revealed fundamental challenges that point to broader research questions in GeoAI:

- For vector-based learning, a key issue is representation (Huang, Khoshelham, and Tomko 2025). How should vector geometries be encoded for sequence-based models such as LSTMs

or transformers? Common formats like WKT or WKB are syntactic encodings rather than semantic ones, and it remains unclear whether they are useful for learning spatial relations.

- For raster-based learning, rasterization itself introduces well-known conceptual challenges (Winter and Frank 2000). When vector geometries are rasterized, spatial relations can change or new relations can emerge that do not exist in the continuous vector domain (e.g., two points “touching” due to pixel adjacency). This longstanding issue in GIScience raises the question of how spatial relations should be formally defined in raster space in order to support meaningful and consistent learning by AI models.

As an exploratory extension, we also investigated whether models trained only on simple geometries could generalize to more complex shapes. Initial experiments using the trained vector models on more complex geometries currently show limited performance, indicating that transferring learned topological concepts from simple to more complex spatial objects remains an open challenge.

This work positions DE-9IM not only as a computational tool but also as a testbed for studying how AI systems learn spatial knowledge. By examining what models learn when trained on fundamental spatial relations, we gain insight into the alignment, or misalignment, between neural representations and established GIScience theory. Ultimately, this line of research contributes to a deeper understanding of spatial conceptualization in AI and provides guidance for designing representations and learning paradigms that respect the unique nature of geospatial data. While this study focuses on sequence- and image-based architectures as a controlled comparison of representation paradigms, graph-based approaches such as Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) represent a natural extension for modeling spatial relations and are part of ongoing work.

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